

MoveD – ORD Guidelines for Swiss Movement Laboratories

Plan / Design

Michelle C. Haas¹, Bettina B. Sommer¹, Simon van Rekum², Felix Moerman³, Eveline S. Graf¹

¹ ZHAW Zurich University of Applied Sciences, School of Health Sciences

² ZHAW Zurich University of Applied Sciences, University Library

³ ZHAW Zurich University of Applied Sciences, President's Office

1. Considerations

Several considerations have to be taken into account when the data from a project in a movement laboratory is to be shared. Please pay special attention to the following points in the corresponding documents:

- Informed consent requirements: Collect – Informed consent with reference to data sharing and Share – Informed consent
- Description of source code: Process – Source code
- Licence types: Share - Licences
- Requirements for SNF and EU projects: Share – Choose a repository
- Quality check of data from others: Reuse – Quality check

Staffing requirements can be found in the standards of GAMMA, Clinical Practice Recommendations from Phillips et al. (2023) or Clinical Movement Analysis Standards by Stewart et al. (2023).

2. References

GAMMA Standards Gang- und Bewegungsanalyse (2024): <https://www.g-a-m-m-a.org/laufende-projekte/standardisierung/>

Phillips, T., Brierty, A., Goodchild, D., Patrilli, B. L., Murphy, A., Boocock, M., Dwan, L., Passmore, E., McGrath, M., & Edwards, J. (2023). Australia and New Zealand Clinical Motion Analysis Group (ANZ-CMAG) clinical practice recommendations. *Gait & Posture*, 106, 1–10. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.gaitpost.2023.07.001>

Stewart, C., Eve, L., Durham, S., Holmes, G., Stebbins, J., Harrington, M., Corbett, M., Kiernan, D., Kidgell, V., Jarvis, S., Daly, C., & Noble, J. (2023). Clinical Movement Analysis Society – UK and Ireland: Clinical Movement Analysis Standards. *Gait & Posture*, 106, 86–94. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.gaitpost.2023.08.006>